

Relationship between CSR and firms' Financial Performance: Empirical Evidence from Indian Banks

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Abstract

Plethora of researches is conducted to ascertain influence of corporate social responsibility (CSR) on financial performance (FP) of firms, and results vary widely. The reason for such varied findings may be due to erroneous analysis or because of insignificant controlled variables considered for current study. We intend to explore the relationship between CSR and financial performance in the Indian banking sector. Data have been gathered from 8 banks, for period of 10 years (2009-2018). The result indicates negative impact of CSR on profitability and no impact on the Earning per Share.

Introduction

The corporate industries across the globe were forced to rethink the relationship they share with the shareholders after the financial crisis in 1929. It is believed that it is not possible for any business to succeed without the support of the immediate society and other stakeholders. European Commission (2001) defined "CSR as a concept whereby companies integrate social and environmental concerns in their business operations and in their interaction with their stakeholders on the voluntary basis". AB Carroll defines CSR as "corporate social responsibility involves the conduct of a business so that it is economically profitable, law-abiding, ethical and socially supportive" (Carroll, 1983).

In recent year, from over few decades, companies have realized and started to invest parts of their profit towards the society in area of education, environment and development etc. which has motivated researchers and academicians to investigate if doing CSR has competitive advantage. There has been mixed results on the studies done by researchers, there are some studies which asserts that expenditure on CSR enhances FP of firms (Margolis, Elfenbein, & Walsh, 2009), there are some studies which feel that spending on CSR activities merely effects the profit of firm as it involves cost associated with it (Friedman, 1970).

Review of Literature

Preceding Studies undertaken to ascertain relationship between CSR and financial performance have revealed varied conclusions, which could be segregated into positive, negative and neutral relationship between CSR and FP.

Positive relationship between CSR and FP

According to the stakeholder theory, CSR has positive impact on the financial performance of a firm. There are literatures available which do support the positive impact of CSR on FP, Waddock and Graves (1997) took 469 firms for their study, and examined impact of firm slack resources as well as the good management theory. They concluded that there was positive association between CSR and FP, it therefore supports both slack resources

and good management theory. Another study conducted by Hammond and Slocum (1996) revealed, CSR can enhance the prominence of the firm thereby reduction in the financial risks, which implies that firms which are associated with CSR have lesser chances of bankruptcy in comparison with non-CSR firms.

Negative relationship between CSR and FP

In late 60s, Milton Friedman came up with the argument that the sole purpose of business is to increase profitability at the same time abiding by the legal and ethical decorum (Friedman, 1970). And this very thought of Friedman was supported by several empirical studies across the globe, for instance, Cordeiro and Sarkis (1997) in a study of 523 US firms argue that there lies a negative correlation between the environmental activism and earning per share. They argued that those firms engaged in the CSR activities are at competitive weakness because they spend on such activities which are to be done by other institutions.

Neutral relationship between CSR and FP

At the same time there are some literary evidence which proves that CSR and FP are two independent variables mutually exclusive, and if any relation does exist between the two, it is only by chance. For instance, McWilliams and Siegel (2000) taking sample of 524 firms for time period of 6 years, investigated the relationship between CSR and FP by incorporating R&D, the results showed neutral effect of CSR on FP. There are number of studies such as Ullmann (1985), Abbott and Monsen (1979), and Griffin and Mahon (1997) which suggest that there are so many variables between corporate social responsibility and financial performance that, there hardly exists any relationship between the two variables and therefore they are mutually exclusive.

Objective

The study intends to examine the relationship between the CSR and Financial Performance of the selected banks in India.

Methodology

Data for the present study has been collected from secondary sources for eight (8) banks, operating in India, for over a period of 10 years (2009-2018). The CSR expenditure of each banks are extracted and calculated from the annual reports, sustainability reports of each banks. Further, other secondary sources has been referred to, for gaining access to the data related to financial parameters such as the Net profit, Total Assets, which has been used in the present study. Correlation and regression methods are used to find the cause and effect relationship between CSR and impact on financial performance of the firm.

Table 1: Definition of Variables

Variable Definition	
CSR	Ratio of CSR Spending on net profit
Profitability	Ratio of Net Profit and Total Assets
Size	Natural Logarithm of Total Assets
DE Ratio	Ratio of Debt and Equity
EPS	Net Profit per share

Source: Own Elaboration

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Median	SD	MIN	Max
CSR	1.750	0.754	6.680	-1.725	48.524
Profitability	0.009	0.011	0.007	-0.010	0.017
EPS	46.543	26.215	48.816	-23.195	144.000
Size	12.949	12.963	0.814	11.104	14.532
DERatio	11.818	12.915	4.312	5.813	18.950

Source: Authors' own calculation

A cursory look into the table reveals that Mean & Median values of all the variables except EPS are more or less similar which gives an indication that the variables are symmetrically distributed. Further the SD indicates that there is enough variation in all the variables to carry out meaningful econometric analysis. All the variables are winsorised at the 5th and 95th percentile (Flannery and Rangan, 2006) for avoiding the influence of extreme observations.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

Variables	Profitability	EPS	CSR	Size	DE Ratio
Profitability	1				
EPS	0.4414*	1			
CSR	-0.0597	-0.0963	1		
Size	-0.3279*	0.1188	0.055	1	
DE Ratio	-0.6906*	0.0628	-0.1566	0.305***	1

Source: Authors' own calculation

The above table explains the correlation between the variables. There is positive correlation between profitability and EPS & at 1% significance level which depicts that increase in profitability leads to higher EPS. There is negative correlation between profitability and size at 1% significance level. Profitability and DE Ratio are negatively correlated at 1% significance level, which justifies the argument of Pecking order theory of Capital structure (Myers, 1984; Myers and Majluf, 1984). There lies positive correlation between size and DE Ratio at 5% significance level which suggests that larger firms have better access in the market and therefore can afford more debt in capital structure (Frank and Goyal, 2003).

Table 4: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

Variable	Profitability	EPS
CSR	1.15	1.15
Size	1.33	1.33
DE Ratio	1.25	1.25
year		
2010	2.99	2.99
2011	3.01	3.01
2012	3.05	3.05
2013	7.24	7.24
2014	7.32	7.32
2015	8.18	8.18
2016	8.26	8.26
2017	7.53	7.53
2018	8.39	8.39

Source: Authors' own calculation

Multicollinearity is expected to be severe if the value of VIF is higher than 10 (Gujaratiet al.,2012).Table 4, checks the VIF values of each independent variable against the dependent variables for multicollinearity and the highest value in any case is 8.39, which shows that we can go for regression analysis and multicollinearity is not matter of concern.

Table 5: Regression Result (Profitability)

Variable	Profitability		
	Pooled OLS	Random Effect(RE)	Fixed Effect(FE)
Constant	0.015198 (1.74)***	0.0151984 (1.74)***	-0.0629465 (-1.47)
CSR	-0.00016 (-2.09)**	-0.0001621 (-2.09)**	-0.0001868 (-2.62)**
Size	0.001681 (-2.35)**	0.0016811 (2.35)**	0.0071041 (2.17)**
DE Ratio	-0.00182 (-13.74)*	-0.001822 (-13.74)*	-0.0010477 (-2.26)**
year			
2010	-0.0041 (-0.95)	-0.0040954 (-0.95)	-0.0028798 (-0.75)
2011	-0.00186 (-0.43)	-0.0018644 (-0.43)	-0.0033757 (-0.85)
2012	-0.00287 (-0.66)	-0.0028704 (-0.66)	-0.0041034 (-0.99)
2013	-0.00422 (-1.12)	-0.0042217 (-1.12)	-0.0048132 (-1.15)
2014	-0.00597 (-1.57)	-0.0059668 (-1.57)	-0.0068908 (-1.57)
2015	-0.00613 (-1.62)	-0.0061281 (-1.62)	-0.0084028 (-1.85)***
2016	-0.01173 (-3.08)*	-0.0117346 (-3.08)*	-0.015084 (-3.12)*
2017	-0.00938 (-2.44)**	-0.0093822 (-2.44)**	-0.0137552 (-2.7)**
2018	-0.01221 (-3.18)*	-0.0122143 (-3.18)*	-0.0170703 (-3.25)*
Adjusted R²	0.827	0.8677	0.8813
Wald test (1)	(21.31)*	(255.74)*	(9.59)*
Wald test (2)	(66.75)*	(200.26)*	(6.27)*
Wald test (3)	(5.39)*	(48.52)*	(4.47)*
Breusch-Pagan test		0.95	
Hausman Test		0.97	

Source: Authors' own calculation

- Notes: (1) Figures in parenthesis under FE are z-statistics, and others are t-statistics
(2) *,** and *** denotes coefficients are statistically significant at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.
(3) Values in parenthesis for Wald test are F-statistics.
(4) Values corresponding to Breusch-pagan and Hausman tests are probability values of χ^2 statistics.

Table 5 provides regression results of the model where profitability is taken as dependent variable. The study uses three estimation techniques i.e. Pooled OLS, FE and RE techniques and results are provided accordingly. The study uses BP test and Hausman test to check the presence of panel specific effect in the model. As the table reveals, neither BP test nor Hausman test statistics are statistically significant, which implies pooled OLS is the appropriate estimation technique in this case. CSR is negatively affecting profitability. Size has positive impact on profitability, which suggests that larger firms have higher profitability than the smaller firms. DE Ratio has negative impact on profitability which suggests that the leverage increases the profitability of firm decreases. Adjusted R² value is 0.827 which indicates that the independent variable used in the models explains about 83% of the variation in the dependent variable. Wald test 1, Wald test 2 and Wald test 3 respectively checks the joint significance of all the variables, independent variables except time dummies and time dummies under the null hypothesis of zero (0) joint significance. The result of the table reveals that all Wald test statistics are statistically significant which suggest that the independent variables used in the model are important and the model is appropriate.

Table 6: Regression Result (EPS)

Variable	EPS		
	Pooled OLS	Random Effect	Fixed Effect
Constant	-178.7929 (-2.28)**	-178.7929 (-2.28)**	-750.9846 (-1.71)***
CSR	-0.2656801 (-0.38)	-0.2656801 (-0.38)	-0.6090292 (-0.83)
Size	22.87934 (3.56)*	22.87934 (3.56)*	68.94371 (2.06)**
DE Ratio	-3.419237 (-2.88)*	-3.419237 (-2.88)*	-3.042854 (-0.64)
Year			
2010	25.26823 (0.65)	25.26823 (0.65)	18.89443 (0.48)
2011	23.1307 (0.6)	23.1307 (0.6)	5.737733 (0.14)
2012	40.08007 (1.03)	40.08007 (1.03)	17.39473 (0.41)
2013	8.600067 (0.25)	8.600067 (0.25)	-20.32063 (-0.48)
2014	-15.22961 (-0.45)	-15.22961 (-0.45)	-48.7905 (-1.09)
2015	-63.02568 (-1.85)***	-63.02568 (-1.85)***	-104.7107 (-2.25)**
2016	-78.58223 (-2.3)**	-78.58223 (-2.3)**	-126.8043 (-2.56)**
2017	-72.03278 (-2.09)**	-72.03278 (-2.09)**	-123.3421 (-2.37)**
2018	-80.49962 (-2.34)**	-80.49962 (-2.34)**	-134.8766 (-2.51)**
Adjusted R2	0.6117	0.703	0.6532
Wald test (1)	(7.69)*	(92.33)*	(6.89)*
Wald test (2)	(5.11)**	(15.34)*	(2.2)

Wald test (3)	(9.53)*	(85.8)*	(5.36)*
Breusch-Pagan test		0.92	
Hausman Test		0.93	

Source: Authors' own calculation

Notes: (1) Figures in parenthesis under FE are z-statistics, and others are t-statistics

(2) *,** and *** denotes coefficients are statistically significant at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

(3) Values in parenthesis for Wald test are F-statistics

(4) Values corresponding to Breusch-pagan and Hausman tests are probability values of χ^2 statistics.

Table 6 provides regression results of the model where EPS is taken as dependent variable. Like table 5, in case of table 6 also results are provided for three estimation techniques i.e. Pooled OLS, FE and RE techniques. Similar to profitability, in case of EPS also the BP test and the Hausman test statistics are statistically insignificant and therefore, pooled OLS estimates are considered to be most appropriate.

Adjusted R^2 value is 0.827 which indicates that the independent variable used in the models explains about 83% of the variation in the dependent variable. Wald test 1, Wald test 2 and Wald test 3 respectively checks the joint significance of all the variables, independent variables except time dummies and time dummies under the null hypothesis of zero (0) joint significance. The result of the table reveals that all Wald test statistics are statistically significant which suggest that the independent variables used in the model are important and the model is appropriate.

Concluding Remarks

The concept of CSR has come into being not long ago and the firms soon realised after the financial crisis faced during 1924, the importance of relationship with the stakeholders. It resulted in number of studies on CSR and its relation with FP, and there was mixed results in the findings. Studies done by Waddock and Graves (1997) & Hammond and Slocum (1996), argued that CSR has effect on FP, at the same time, some studies argued against negative relationship between the two variables (Cordeiro and Sarkis (1997) and McWilliams and Siegel (2000), Ullmann (1985), Abbott and Monsen (1979), and Griffin and Mahon (1997) were against any sort of relationship between CSR and FP. Though there are number of studies on the topic, but literature fails to provide conclusive results. There are number of studies conducted across different sectors, and there has been mixed results. Garai (2016), in an attempt to find the relation between CSR and FP, came to a conclusion that CSR did not impact the financial performance, rather it was some other reasons for the growth in Net profit of RIL. Arshadet. al. (2015), in their study on the similar topic concluded that CSR does not impact financial performance in the short term scenario.

Therefore the study intends to provide some empirical evidence, for which panel data of 8 banks have been collected for time period of 10 years. Profitability and Earning per Share are two dependent variables, and size, debt equity ratio, are the two control variables. The result shows CSR negatively impacts profitability and CSR has no impact on EPS.

This study also has some important implications for the managers, involved in the decision making and policy formulations for carrying out CSR. Managers may decide to engage in social responsibility activities based on their values, at the same time efficiency of the managers will also have impact on the increase in the net profit of the firms. However, in the long run, business strategies and public policy resemble driverseven though the role of

consumer behavior fluctuates irregularly between driver and effector for earning profit and serving society.

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